

Minimization of Hidden Toxic and Technological Risks in Scaffold Fabrication Exemplified by Human Artery Scaffold Production

Anton E. Trostin^{1*}

¹Eternal is real LLC, Chelyabinsk, Russia

*antontrostin@yahoo.com

ORCID: orcid.org/0009-0009-7254-2099

Note: This is an early-stage preprint. In the current revision, visual materials (Figures), as well as method validation are unavailable and will be included in subsequent updates.

Currently, numerous methods exist for fabricating scaffolds; however, many are accompanied by both overt and hidden risks. Therefore, the authors proposed a protocol for the mold casting method, using the creation of a human artery scaffold as an example, to minimize toxic and technological risks. A sodium alginate – calcium chloride complex was used as the test scaffold components. The anti-adhesion stage employed a method of eliminating adhesion based on the difference in coefficients of thermal expansion. A design for a casting mold to produce a vascular frame shape was proposed, along with a design for a device for concentrating solutions via evaporation.

Introduction

Currently, a wide arsenal of methods has been developed for scaffold fabrication. The primary methods include bioprinting, mold casting techniques, stereolithography (SLA/DLP), electrospinning, and many others [1,2]. One of the key issues common to many scaffold fabrication processes is hidden toxic and technological risks, which pose a significant hazard. These risks were analyzed, and subsequently, a scaffold fabrication protocol was developed to minimize their presence. A list of these risks is provided below.

The first conditional category encompasses the transformation of organic components into aldehydes under specific conditions. The resulting substances, such as formaldehyde and many others, may not only be present as volatile organic compounds (VOCs) but can also remain within the volume of the component subjected to the impact. For this reason, washing may be insufficient due to the accumulation of transformation products. It should also be considered that VOCs have specific odors depending on the type of organic component; however, the absence of odor is not an indicator

of the absence of VOCs. Therefore, to minimize risks, it is necessary to use gas detectors (HCHO, TVOC).

Organic components in this context include not only any biological entities by definition but also technical components that may be subjected to heating during the assembly and operation of biotechnical devices. These include: components for electronics soldering (fluxes[3], solder pastes[4], and protective masks[5]); epoxy resins[6], adhesives[7], varnishes, and paints[8] (which emit volatile organic compounds (VOCs) even without heating, at room temperature[8-10]); polymers in the form of plastic casings for electronic microcircuits and mechanical parts, including those produced via polymer printing (where plastic from a spool is heated to enable layer adhesion[11]) and printing using photopolymer resins (the use of photopolymer resins in polymer printing itself causes the formation of VOCs, including aldehydes[12]); as well as polymer hoses for air and water and various insulating components[13]. Fluoroplastics (e.g., PTFE) are organic components (polymers) more resistant to this type of reaction (however, for instance, exceeding a certain temperature also leads to the release of hazardous compounds)[14].

One of the conditions for the aldehyde formation reaction is the thermal impact on an organic component when the temperature exceeds a certain threshold[15]; this threshold directly depends on the type of heated component.

Temperature can also be a factor increasing the degree of the exogenous Maillard reaction (glycation)[16]: upon contact between amino groups (proteins, amino acids) and carbonyl groups (sugars, polysaccharides, glucose, fructose), aldehydes are formed.

The temporal factor alone can also become a condition for aldehyde formation: over months or years of storage, depending on the type of organic component, an accumulation of various carbonyl compounds, including aldehydes, occurs[17]. This is one of the reasons for product expiration dates.

Oxidation of organic components also serves as a condition for aldehyde formation[18]. In the context of this work, it is essential to distinguish between 'oxidizing agents' and 'acids', as they play fundamentally different roles: oxidation is a process of electron transfer from a substrate to an oxidizing agent; acids, on the other hand, are substances that create a low-pH environment, which catalyzes the hydrolysis of acetals to form aldehydes.

Oxidizing agents (with varying oxidizing capacities) include: molecular oxygen (O₂)[19] (lowest intensity, yet present in the air (non-aqueous)

environment, thus constituting a constant condition in most processes and can be catalyzed by various mechanisms); ozone[20]; and free radicals[21] (possess the highest oxidizing capacity), such as hydroxyl or mechanoradicals; as well as certain acids and solutions, such as sodium hypochlorite, hydrogen peroxide, potassium permanganate, and sulfuric, nitric, and peracetic acids. Among these, only KMnO_4 (potassium permanganate) is non-volatile at room temperature.

Free radicals, in turn, are generated by exposure to electric current[22], contact with transition-valence metals[23], exposure to low-temperature plasma[24], and intensive dispersion (mixing)[25]. Metals with transition valence include: titanium; platinum, silver, gold, copper, iron, tungsten, molybdenum, zirconium, and other active metals. Notably, titanium dioxide, which coats titanium, generates free radicals under light. Lewis acid ions (Al^{3+} , Zn^{2+} , Sn^{4+} , Ti^{4+}) act as catalysts for this process (aldehyde formation)[26].

Intensive dispersion (e.g., blending), in particular, not only leads to the formation of hydroxyl radicals but also increases contact with oxygen, which in turn enhances the intensity of oxidative processes. Furthermore, mechanical destruction in more intensive dispersers, specifically homogenizers or ball mills, also causes aldehyde formation due to a high degree of mechanical destruction and the generation of free radicals[27].

An alkaline environment also serves as a condition for the formation of aldehydes from sugars [28,29], as well as an intensifying factor for aldehyde formation from organic components[30].

Ozonolysis (exposure to ozone) can also be a condition for aldehyde formation[31]. Notably, ozone is also generated by light in the UV range. Accordingly, exposure to light is another condition for this process[32]. The intensity and duration of light exposure play a crucial role. This fundamental photochemical process underlies the recommendations for storing biomaterials (in closed, light-proof packaging). The UV spectrum, which includes sunlight, has a greater impact on this process than artificial light in the visible range. However, even light outside the UV range, particularly in the blue spectrum, can contribute to aldehyde formation, especially under conditions of high intensity (brightness) and prolonged exposure (photobioreactors)[33]. This degradation leading to aldehyde formation is enhanced in the presence of certain substances within the organic component (e.g., photounstable elements in sunscreens)[34].

The second conditional category includes the formation of hexavalent chromium when using chromium-containing metals or coatings. The most common among these are: most types of alloyed steels (including every type of stainless steel and galvanized steel with chromate passivation); nichrome wire (heating elements); some alloyed aluminum alloys; as well as various chrome-plated components made of metals or polymers.

The fundamental process for the transition of chromium to its hexavalent form is oxidation – the transfer of electrons from a chromium atom to an oxidizing agent[35]. Thus, oxidation and electrochemical processes are determining factors (accordingly, in these processes, alkali also acts as a catalyst, while temperature is a kinetic factor influencing the reaction rate).

Consequently, one of the common conditions for the formation of hexavalent chromium from its safe state is high-temperature treatment in the presence of oxygen, but at temperatures higher than those required for aldehyde formation from organic components[36,37]. This is relevant for metalworking processes occurring under frictional conditions due to loads generated by mechanical drives without sufficient cooling (drilling, etc.). In such cases, cooling using organic components inevitably leads to the release of aldehydes, as mentioned earlier. This is also relevant for thermal metal processing methods (welding, etc.). A key factor in these processes is that, although chromium is reduced to its safe form after cooling, this occurs due to the presence of that portion of the volume that retained chromium's safe form and acted as a reducing agent for the hexavalent form. However, a critically important condition is direct atomic interaction: the hexavalent form is reduced to its safe state only upon direct contact with the safe form[38]. Therefore, by-products such as scale (the portion mixed with other components, preventing direct contact with the safe part of the product) and aerosols (metal dust, the quantity of which in these processes can be comparable to equally hazardous wood dust[39,40]), which are generated during these processes, contain hexavalent chromium in a stable and unalterable form.

Another common condition for hexavalent chromium formation is exposure to electric current[41,42]. During electrochemical processes, chromium is released from the metal matrix as products of electrochemical destruction (precipitates). These precipitates are easily washed away and pose a risk of contaminating adjacent surfaces and the fluids passing through them (water supply). It is fundamentally important that such precipitates are not reduced upon contact with metal that has retained chromium's safe form: they are stable over time and require specialized deactivation[43,44].

Thus, the scenarios for this condition are classified into two categories: direct contact with metal surfaces; and the use of fluids passing through them. Control is complicated by the absence of organoleptic markers for this process. Nevertheless, specialized indicator test strips have been developed for detecting hexavalent chromium on metal surfaces[45], while digital colorimeters are used for monitoring aqueous environments[46]. As a risk minimization measure in water supply systems, the application of reverse osmosis systems is recommended[47]. Furthermore, fluid heating systems should be equipped with ceramic heating elements in areas of direct contact with the working medium to prevent electrochemical chromium emission.

The next conditional category includes the sterilization process. This process poses a hazard due to its destructive effect on organic components. Additionally, a danger of this process is that intermediate breakdown products—aldehydes—may remain after the destruction of organic components. In this regard, the use of paper sterilization bags (kraft bags) appears impractical, as they consist of organic components[48]. In this context, the use of multi-layer aluminum foil is more justified due to its inert, inorganic composition. However, it should be considered that even the sterilization of inorganic components carries risks: the presence of residual organic contaminants (lipids and other biological media) on their surfaces can also lead to the formation of breakdown products, including aldehydes. Distilled water, in turn, also contains organic contaminants. It should also be noted that some types of sterilization can initiate the formation of hexavalent chromium or act as factors increasing the intensity of this process.

Sterilization methods are categorized based on the type of exposure. The most accessible are thermal methods, which pose a hazard because temperature exposure is one of the most common causes of aldehyde generation. Although raising the temperature from +121°C (the average autoclaving temperature, sufficient for aldehyde formation from some components), for example, to +180°C (air sterilization, "dry heat") initiates the destruction of aldehydes themselves (mineralization[49]), intermediate breakdown products (aldehydes) may still have time to be released into the volume of the heated component and into the air. The situation is further complicated by the fact that air sterilizers are not equipped with exhaust gas filtration systems, which facilitates the penetration of breakdown products (aldehydes) into the surrounding space. It is also necessary to consider that the electrical insulation of live parts in dry-heat sterilization devices, depending on their design, may be made from less heat-resistant components (e.g., PVC-based). This, in turn, can lead to additional aldehyde formation. While muffle furnaces lack organic components in their construction, they

also lack filtration systems, similarly leading to the release of aldehydes into the environment.

In addition to thermal sterilization, as well as UV and ozone sterilization, there are also less hazardous types, though they still pose a threat. In particular, sterilization with hydrogen peroxide and plasma sterilization pose a lesser threat in the context of aldehyde formation[50]. However, the hydrogen peroxide sterilization process takes a considerable amount of time, and consequently, there is a risk of the reaction stopping at an intermediate stage due to various conditions, at which aldehydes are present. Furthermore, hydrogen peroxide is more capable of leading to aldehyde formation upon contact with certain components, such as: alcohols[51], as well as unreacted residues of hardened photopolymer printed products[52] (methacrylates, acrylates). It should also be noted that since hydrogen peroxide, as mentioned earlier, can lead to the appearance of hydroxyl radicals, contact with it should be avoided (e.g., using it to treat wounds). Moreover, since hydrogen peroxide vapor is volatile, inhalation of its vapors also poses a significant risk.

Interest is drawn to a recently proposed sterilization method using a critical level of carbon dioxide[53]. This method is theoretically entirely safe but carries a prohibitively high cost, making it inaccessible for most budget-conscious organizations. Nevertheless, there are studies in which a DIY device was assembled to implement this sterilization method[54]. It can thus be hypothesized that with the future advancement of more accessible applications of this technology, it may become possible to sterilize organic scaffolds entirely after their final geometry formation, without risk to the operator and without toxic byproducts from the sterilization process.

Meanwhile, substances such as ethanol and other alcohols are disinfectants, not sterilizing agents, due to their ineffectiveness against spores[55]. Syringe filtration is also not a sterilization method because it is ineffective against viruses, as the sizes of viruses (and aldehydes) are significantly smaller than the pore sizes in syringe filters[56,57]. It should also be considered that if the filter membrane is made from components unstable to aggressive media (e.g., oxidizers), such filters themselves can become a source of contamination (aldehyde formation). The remaining sterilization methods pose an elevated hazard.

The final category can include impurities and steps that are directly present in either an explicit or hidden form. Explicit examples here are: the use of alloying components such as chromium, nickel, cobalt, and vanadium[58]; the addition of fiberglass to enhance heat resistance and physico-mechanical

properties (e.g., for manufacturing electrical insulation wiring, air/liquid delivery systems, and other products[59]); aggressive steps of chemical cross-linking (e.g., using glutaraldehyde[60]); as well as the application of reagents directly initiating aldehyde formation (for instance, the treatment of sodium alginate with NaIO_4 [61]).

Hidden factors include impurities present below the mandatory declaration threshold in composition or specifications, or those not subject to mandatory declaration. Examples of these may include: aldehydes in chemical solvents; alloying additives in metals; fiberglass in the construction of various devices; impurities of transition-valence metals within the metals themselves, as well as in clay, paraffin, alginate, and other products; and polysaccharides in biological components (e.g., in commercial versions of transglutaminase). This category also encompasses vacuum processing, which is accompanied by the desorption of substances previously trapped in the working volume[62].

In this context, personal protective equipment such as respirators cannot guarantee complete protection due to individual facial structure variations: respirators reduce but do not entirely block the ingress of toxic air into the respiratory tract. Fume hoods also reduce but do not completely eliminate toxins from the air. Filters, in turn, themselves become a source of contamination over time, especially under elevated temperature operating conditions, and situations may arise where their frequent and timely replacement is not feasible. Concurrently, ensuring the complete removal of residues in the finished scaffold is also currently impossible in any existing methodology, regardless of the process type.

Consequently, there is a need for a method free from the aforementioned risks. Thus, the authors of the present work propose a protocol for obtaining scaffolds with minimal risks, tested on a human artery scaffold. This protocol is based on the mold casting method. A device design for concentrating solutions via evaporation after syringe filtration was proposed, and tests of its toxicity to the surrounding workspace were conducted. Furthermore, a casting mold design was proposed, enabling piston extrusion directly into the cross-linking solution, thereby forming the final vascular frame shape. Sodium alginate in combination with calcium chloride served as the test components[63]; for the anti-adhesion stage, a method eliminating adhesion based on the difference in coefficients of thermal expansion was employed.

Results

Device for Solution Concentration via Evaporation

The concentration of VOCs (TVOC, HCHO) was measured using a gas detector. Air toxicity was measured inside a powered-down, open-type laminar flow hood with the device operational. Measurements were conducted for 5 minutes in each zone (Figure 1), as well as in the laboratory space, after which the maximum value for each zone was recorded.

The maximum VOC value (HCHO/TVOC) was: near the heating elements (working vessel) (1a) N mg/m³; near the control unit at a constant distance of 10 cm (1b) N mg/m³; in the open space of the laminar flow hood N mg/m³; within the laboratory space N mg/m³.

Figure 1. Zones for measuring threshold VOC levels.

Formation of the Arterial Vascular Scaffold

The preliminary assessment of the processability of the sodium alginate (NaAlg) solution revealed limitations of the syringe filtration method. The maximum achievable concentration for successful extrusion through a syringe filter was 1% (w/v), which defined the concentration range for subsequent molding experiments.

To assess the influence of polymer concentration on geometric stability (shape retention), the alginate solution was cooled to +4°C and then extracted from a cylindrical mold into a 1.1% CaCl₂ cross-linking solution.

Figure 2a shows a photograph of the result after extracting a sample containing only 1% (w/v) NaAlg from the mold. Despite pre-cooling to +4°C and extraction into a cooled (+4°C) cross-linking agent solution, the sample demonstrated a complete lack of structural stability and an inability to retain the designated cylindrical geometry. This outcome is attributed to insufficient gel strength at this concentration. Pre-freezing also did not improve the sample's geometry upon extraction (2b): although the sample maintained structural stability while in a crystallized state after freezing (-18°C), upon thawing in the cross-linking solution, the walls began to deform (spread). This proves the necessity of increasing the solution concentration after the syringe filtration stage.

Increasing the concentration to 2.5% led to a significant rise in solution viscosity and the elasticity of the forming hydrogel (2c). This allowed the material to withstand mechanical stresses during extraction from the casting mold, ensuring the production of an item with a high degree of reproducibility of the designated geometry. The obtained sample demonstrated a smooth surface and replicated the geometry of the casting mold.

Performing preliminary cycles of thermostating (+41°C) and freezing (-18°C) of the concentrated 2.5% (w/v) NaAlg solution poured into the casting mold, followed by extrusion from the mold into a cooled cross-linking solution (+4°C), did not alter the geometry. This proves the absence of influence of the anti-adhesion method, based on the difference in coefficients of thermal expansion, on the reproduction of the designated cylindrical shape (2d).

In turn, using a concentration obtained by evaporating a 1% (w/v) solution for 2 hours at a temperature of +41°C also resulted in the reproduction of the designated cylindrical geometry (2e). In this case, the initial volume of the alginate solution, 2 ml, decreased to 0,N ml, indicating a loss of volume during device operation, which is the objective of this equipment. The comparability of these results with those obtained using a pre-prepared 2.5% concentration solution (2c) demonstrates that increasing the 1% concentration to a functional level also confirms the operational viability of the design.

(Image of scaffolds)

Figure 2. Photographs of the results of forming vascular constructs with a diameter of 4x6 mm. (2a) – 1% (w/v) NaAlg without pre-freezing. (2b) – 1%

(w/v) NaAlg with pre-freezing. (2c) – 2.5% (w/v) NaAlg without pre-freezing. (2d) – 2.5% (w/v) NaAlg with pre-freezing. (2e) – result of the device's operation. Each sample was pre-cooled (+4°C).

Discussion

Final Protocol

Thus, considering the information from the provided review and the obtained research results, a protocol for scaffold fabrication with minimal toxic and technological risks can be compiled:

A) Selection of scaffold components and the evaporator's working vessel.

Use synthetic polymers (e.g., polyethylene glycol[64]) as scaffold components. This type of polymer does not contain biological substrates that promote viral contamination, unlike biopolymers of animal origin. This allows limiting the preparation of scaffold components to the method of syringe filtration followed by evaporation, thereby avoiding the aforementioned risks associated with sterilization processes and peptide degradation. The use of synthetic polymers also subsequently reduces the degree of the Maillard reaction. Furthermore, when functionalizing this polymer to PEG-GL[65] and attaching[66] MMP-sensitive and adhesive peptides (e.g., RGD), the polymer becomes fully bioactive and capable of enzymatic cross-linking by transglutaminase (mTGase), similar to protein scaffold components such as collagen or gelatin. The working vessel of the evaporator should be made of a polymer with maximum resistance to aggressive media in the context of aldehyde formation.

B) Fabrication of a negative casting mold.

For vascular (non-branching) casting molds, these can be fluoroplastic cylinders with intermediate metal rods for rigidity (as presented in this work).

For fabricating objects of complex configuration, fluoroplastic-2 (polyvinylidene fluoride, PVDF) is an effective material. The choice of this polymer is dictated by its thermophysical properties, particularly the correlation between its melting and thermal degradation temperatures and the associated release of aldehydes. The manufacturing process involves the preliminary creation of a master mold via CNC milling of blanks from non-ferrous metals (aluminum or brass alloys). Subsequently, the metal tooling is heated to approximately 150 °C and pressed into a PVDF blank preheated to similar temperatures. The thermal exposure is implemented based on the principle of the evaporator's working vessel operation: an aluminum base

heated by two thermal blocks is used to secure the PVDF blank, and the metal mold is also preheated. The temperature regime is empirically selected to establish the minimum threshold of PVDF plasticity sufficient for correct mold release while minimizing the risks of thermal degradation. Since the melting temperature of F-2 initiates the release of volatile aldehydes, the heat treatment process must be conducted outdoors with mandatory use of personal respiratory protection equipment (respirators): the evaporator's design implies the use of 24-volt power, allowing portable power sources (batteries) to operate the device. At the final stage, to eliminate metal ions transferred from the tooling surface, the obtained fluoroplastic mold undergoes treatment in an ethanolic solution of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA).

C) Sterilization.

Scaffold components, as mentioned earlier, undergo syringe filtration; however, casting molds require the use of aggressive types of full sterilization.

At this stage, a significant challenge is posed by persistent forms of contaminants, specifically spores and acetals, as well as residual components of disinfecting and washing solutions. This is due to the fact that spores, like acetals, exhibit high resistance to most types of exposure; meanwhile, acetals undergo hydrolysis to form aldehydes with the slightest shift in pH towards the acidic range. Furthermore, the use of aggressive sterilization solutions capable of destroying spores and acetals carries the risk of retaining residual amounts of reagents that initiate aldehyde formation from the components of the working media (in this case, polyethylene glycol), creating a cyclical process.

Consequently, the optimal solution is a type of exposure that, upon completion, leaves no conditions for aldehydogenesis from PEG, for example, a thermal method (autoclaving): after the process ends, the temperature drops to room level, and the elimination of the key aggression factor stops the reaction. However, as noted earlier, thermal exposure during autoclaving induces the generation of aldehydes both into the air, creating risks during chamber depressurization, and directly into the sterilized object—in this case, the fluoroplastic mold, which may contain organic contaminants. This necessitates an additional stage of aldehyde neutralization.

However, the reagent providing irreversible destruction of aldehydes—sodium borohydride[67]—is incompatible with the autoclaving process due to intensive hydrogen generation, posing a risk of autoclave structural failure

from overpressure. Therefore, the aldehyde elimination stage must be conducted post-factum, after autoclaving.

Directly during the sterilization process, a stage for inhibiting aldehyde emission into the air must be provided: this stage can involve immersing the sterilized object (the fluoroplastic mold) in an inorganic solution that ensures chemisorption of aldehydes with conversion into non-volatile forms. A sodium hydroxide solution can be used as such a binding agent. However, if the aldehyde concentration is very high, a portion of them may bypass the solution along with vapor bubbles before having time to react with NaOH.

It is also necessary to consider that sodium borohydride exhibits inertness towards acetals due to their high chemical resistance. The strategy for destroying acetals is their conversion into corresponding aldehydes via acid-catalyzed hydrolysis. This approach does not initiate the synthesis of new compounds but merely converts persistent acetals into a reactive aldehyde form, which in terms of risk level is identical to the original contaminant, as it readily forms aldehydes upon exposure in acidic environments, an inherent factor in scaffold production technology. Citric acid is proposed as the optimal agent for acid hydrolysis, which, unlike aggressive oxidizers like hydrogen peroxide, acts as a mild organic catalyst. An additional safety factor is the subsequent stage of treatment with sodium borohydride in an alkaline environment, which neutralizes acidic residues and minimizes risks associated with acid use.

The final sterilization and cleaning protocol includes: exposure in NaOH solution; followed by autoclaving also in NaOH solution; then exposure in citric acid solution at elevated temperature (60°C); and subsequently exposure in an ethanolic (ethanol) solution of sodium borohydride in an ultrasonic bath in a high-pH (NaOH) environment. Inter-stage processing includes washing with distilled water and final deactivation in a buffer solution with a neutral pH value.

The sterilized items are incubated for several days in sterile distilled water to completely eliminate trace amounts of the alkaline agent. The water is sterilized using a multi-stage cascade filtration method: preliminary purification is performed by a reverse osmosis system and adsorption on activated carbon (the efficiency of formaldehyde adsorption using activated carbon based on *Hibiscus rosa-sinensis* is 95.49% [68]) to remove metal ions and dissolved organic matter; the final sterilization stage is achieved by passing the water through hydrophilic membrane filters with a pore size of 0.22 μm . This approach eliminates risks associated with aggressive full sterilization processes.

D) Scaffold Fabrication.

The evaporated solution of synthetic polymer, containing a cross-linking agent (mTGase without the maltodextrin additive present in commercial versions) and NaCl crystals[69] (with particle size corresponding to the type of cells to be seeded), is filled into the casting mold.

Inactivation of mTGase is performed passively via substrate depletion by holding in the casting mold at room temperature (for a 5 cm long artery scaffold, the exposure time is approximately 4 hours). This approach eliminates the need for thermal or chemical treatment to inactivate the enzyme, preventing the risk of initiating the Maillard reaction and thermally-induced aldehyde formation.

Extraction of the scaffold from the casting mold is performed using the cryo-anti-adhesion method (elimination of adhesion based on the difference in coefficients of thermal expansion). An increased number of freeze-thaw cycles (compared to the protocol in the present work) is conducted due to the pronounced adhesive properties of the enzyme.

However, the high adhesion of the enzyme can be an advantage: mTGase can be used for covalent cross-linking ("bonding") of multi-component scaffolds, which can be a key quality for forming complex geometries with undercuts when using casting molds. After extraction, the scaffold is rinsed with a buffer solution or distilled water to remove NaCl crystals until isotonic osmotic pressure is achieved.

Sodium alginate and the glass vessel for the evaporator's working space were chosen for preliminary testing due to their accessibility compared to PEG-GL and fluoroplastics. The full implementation of this protocol is the subject for completing the study.

Analysis of Results

Thus, we obtain a scaffold in which the aforementioned risks at all manufacturing stages are minimized.

Due to the compactness of the proposed designs, an advantage of the methodology is the ability to perform each stage directly within the workspace of a laminar flow hood, unlike using standalone external devices (bioprinters), and the entire fabrication process takes a short period of time. However, a drawback is that sterilization is not the final stage of scaffold production.

Evaporation tests were conducted without hydrophobic air filters. However, to prevent contamination, filters should be installed at the Luer-Lock connection ports (Figure 1).

Future work plans include conducting more precise analyses of the ambient air for the presence of aldehydes within the working zone[70].

The proposed evaporation scheme, although complex for achieving precisely reproducible concentrations, still allows for the use of syringe filtration. Concentrations obtained after syringe filtration processes are often unsuitable for some working protocols. Nevertheless, the variation in final concentration values may be acceptable provided that the empirically determined conditions for incubation time and the temperatures of external and internal components are precisely adhered to.

Occupational Health and Safety

However, when creating complex casting molds, a number of specific difficulties must be considered.

In particular, when using CNC milling, high friction between the milling cutter and the workpiece during milling of biocompatible chromium-containing materials such as stainless steels can lead to the release of hexavalent chromium into the surrounding environment. It is also necessary to consider that the cutter, which most likely contains toxic alloying elements, will heat up to temperatures causing hexavalent chromium release. Consequently, particles of these toxic impurities, including the formed hexavalent chromium, can become airborne during intensive machining and remain trapped within the surface of the titanium workpiece due to high adhesion (smearing), potentially later entering the working solutions. Furthermore, in an alkaline environment, chromium forms soluble chromates (yellow solutions) that easily penetrate pores[71]. Additionally, the use of non-specialized cooling fluids raises concerns about overheating the machine's motor, likely containing organic insulating components. Moreover, the use of organic cooling agents leads to aldehyde formation. Conversely, manufacturing molds from soft metals like aluminum or brass requires applying an external coating to them, as their use results in indirect contamination of the solution with metal ions.

Using plastic workpieces inevitably leads to overheating and consequent aldehyde release. The safety of platinum-cured silicone, in turn, is questionable due to unreacted residues.

The Glycation Paradox

However, when the stage of cell seeding into the finished scaffold arrives, the Maillard reaction inevitably becomes an insurmountable obstacle.

The issue is that when we sustain cell life in a medium, we thereby automatically create conditions for a slow, non-enzymatic Maillard reaction (glycation) between the medium components themselves and the cells. Even in their pure form, without a scaffold, cells, being a source of amino groups (membrane proteins, secreted proteins) and endogenous dicarbonyls (methylglyoxal, glyoxal), engage in an uncontrolled glycation reaction with carbonyl compounds in the culture medium. Thus, regardless of the scaffold's nature we choose, we will inevitably enhance one side of an already ongoing reaction: polysaccharide scaffolds (e.g., alginate-based) will react with amino groups from cells, while protein scaffolds (e.g., collagen-based) will react with carbonyl components of the cellular environment.

Nevertheless, there are methods to reduce the degree of glycation. These methods fall into two categories: reducing the level of reaction between the cell culture medium and the cells themselves, and using a specialized material as the scaffold framework.

The first category may include: reducing glucose levels to 5.5 mmol/L; using galactose or mannose as the primary carbohydrate instead of glucose, and especially fructose (which reacts orders of magnitude more readily); using specialized serum-free media to eliminate albumin, which already contains AGEs and numerous amino groups for further glycation; adding glycolysis or glycation inhibitors (e.g., aminoguanidine) to the medium; supplementing the medium with high but non-toxic concentrations of L-arginine or L-lysine; adding glutathione or alpha-lipoic acid.

Furthermore, as a radical approach, a cell culture medium can be formulated individually. In this context, for an artery, such a medium could comprise: Base: a physiological saline solution balanced for ions (Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Cl^-). Energy substrate: galactose / mannose. Amino acids: a complete set, but with elevated levels of arginine and glutamine. Antioxidants: ascorbate, glutathione, or selenium. Buffer: HEPES. Growth factors: recombinant human VEGF, FGF, IGF are added—without animal protein, and thus without pre-existing AGEs.

The second group may include methods aimed at modifying the scaffold. One such method involves using scaffolds based on chemically inert synthetic polymers, such as polyethylene glycol (PEG)[71], which lack reactive amine or carbonyl groups. However, pure PEG is incapable of forming functional hydrogels. To address this, it is controllably functionalized with carbonyl

(glutamine, Gln) and amine groups (lysine, Lys)[72]. As a result, after cross-linking is complete, the risk of spontaneous glycation in such a system becomes orders of magnitude lower than in native protein matrices (e.g., collagen), where many free amino groups remain accessible. This method allows for the creation of a more stable, biocompatible hydrogel, eliminates the use of UV cross-linking and toxic initiators, and reduces the level of reactive groups.

Methods

Bioink Preparation

A sodium alginate (NaAlg) dispersion was obtained via spontaneous hydration. 1% (w/v) and 2.5% (w/v) NaAlg solutions were incubated at room temperature for 24 hours. Subsequent deaeration of the formed foam was achieved by centrifugation at 2500 g for 40 minutes until a homogeneous suspension was obtained. After preparing the solution, a 2 ml aliquot was taken and placed into the device for concentration via thermo-aeration. Processing was conducted for 2 hours, with external heating regulated to stabilize and maintain the temperature within the container's working volume (in situ) at 41°C. Aeration was set at a value of 10 liters per minute. To prevent drying of the NaAlg surface layer, the working vessel was rotated: 45° clockwise and counterclockwise relative to the starting position, with 2-second pauses after each movement. Upon completion of the process, the resulting concentrate was collected using a 1 ml nominal volume syringe.

Device for Concentration via Thermo-aeration

The device is a rotating thermostated reactor for concentrating solutions with a forced aeration system. A photograph of the device is shown in Figure 1.

To minimize heating from excessive friction, mechanical processing (drilling) of parts during device assembly was performed using titanium-coated drill bits. To minimize the generation of fine metal dust, drilling was conducted at reduced speeds with high feed force to ensure the formation of large chips. To control the thermal regime and ensure effective heat dissipation, periodic cooling of the tool in distilled water was employed. The use of cooling fluids based on organic components was excluded due to the risk of aldehyde formation upon contact with the heated tool.

The body of the electronic control unit was made from mild steel to meet the requirements for mechanical processing. Polymer materials were not used for the housing due to the increased probability of local overheating during

drilling and surface finishing. The necessary electrical insulation was ensured by locally insulating each electronic component installed inside the housing.

To prevent ongoing VOC emission from electronic components with organic insulation during operation within the housing, the ventilation system was organized based on the principle of directed airflow onto the central control boards. The top fan creates a downward airflow, providing forced air cooling for the control boards, after which the air is distributed to peripheral zones, encompassing the remaining electronic components. The area of active airflow also includes passive cooling radiators installed on both the power elements of the control boards and other heat-loaded components of the system.

Rotation of the working zone is provided by a stepper motor with reduced torque to minimize heating under conditions of negligible resistance to shaft rotation. The motor platform is made of a soft metal to meet mechanical processing requirements. On the rear side of the motor, a finned radiator is secured via a threaded mount (without the use of thermal interface materials). Motor control is implemented through a stepper motor driver placed on an expansion board within the zone of direct airflow from the forced ventilation system. A standard (factory) aluminum radiator was installed on the driver. The holding current was limited to 0.25 A. To prevent cumulative overheating, a 2-second pause was programmatically implemented after each operating cycle, allowing for relaxation of the temperature field in the absence of internal heat generation.

The working vessel consists of an external aluminum alloy container and an inner container. Heating blocks with installed heating elements and thermistors were attached to the outer side of the external container. The inner container was secured to the external container via a strap using eye bolts.

Holes in the aluminum container were drilled with a metal backing plate placed underneath to prevent bending of the aluminum container walls during drilling. This design ensures a tight fit of the heating blocks against the container walls without the use of external intermediate gaskets.

Ceramic heaters (Artillery Sidewinder, 64 W power) were used as the active heating elements. The choice of this specific model is due to its design features, allowing for the replacement of the standard fiberglass insulation. The standard electrical insulation was removed and replaced with fluoroplastic rods. The power lines (wiring) of the heating elements were extended using wires with silicone electrical insulation.

An NTC100K model thermistor was used, as its construction excludes epoxy resin and features factory-applied fluoroplastic insulation at the points of direct contact between the sensing element and the heated part.

Power control is implemented via a solid-state DC relay mounted on a radiator. Using this combination allows the control boards to function solely as a source of the control signal for closing the power circuit, eliminating heating of the control board traces and the power line.

The PID controller temperature parameters were obtained via auto-calibration in Pronterface (command M303 E-1 C8 S115) and loaded into the Marlin firmware. Limiting the regulator's maximum power (parameter PID_MAX or MAX_BED_POWER to a value of 128) in combination with the configured coefficients ensured a temperature stability accuracy of 0.5°C in steady-state mode.

The setpoint temperature on the heating elements (+115°C) was calibrated considering thermal losses to achieve the required temperature inside the reactor volume (+45°C). Drift in the internal temperature during prolonged operation was compensated for by monitoring with an additional autonomous sensor and real-time temperature adjustment during the device calibration phase.

The device is powered by a 24-volt DC power supply. The use of an elevated voltage (compared to 12 volts) allowed for the reduction of operating currents in the power circuits, thereby minimizing heat generation in active components. Since the device is intended for operation inside a laminar flow hood in a humid environment with a conductive surface (chromium-containing alloy), potential contact points between the device's housing and working vessel and the hood surface were insulated using silicone gaskets. This solution reduces the risks of stray current transmission in a conductive, humid environment and consequently lowers the risk of toxic hexavalent chromium compounds forming on working surfaces (it also eliminates the risk of failure of interconnected electronic equipment due to a short circuit of the device's power circuits to the grounded hood surface).

Aeration of the working vessel was performed using atmospheric air forced by an external membrane vacuum pump with a nominal capacity of 10 L/min. The pump was used as an autonomous module, connected to a separate power supply and not part of the main device system. Airflow regulation was performed via a potentiometer built into the pump's power supply block. To prevent thermal impact from the working vessel on the hydrophobic air filter, which is to be installed at the Luer-Lock connector

(Figure 1), the connection was implemented using a segment of heat-resistant tubing, creating a buffer zone. The tubing was connected to a sealed connector installed in the upper lid of the working vessel. Air exhaust was directed through a second sealed connector in the lid; a second 0.22 μm hydrophobic filter was connected to this connector via similar tubing using the same Luer-Lock system, ensuring a closed system and preventing contamination.

Fabrication of the Artery Scaffold Mold

The artery scaffold mold was fabricated using the mold casting method. The algorithm for mold creation is presented in Figure 3.

(Image of scaffolds/vessels)

Figure 3. Photographs of sequential stages of obtaining the matrix via the mold casting method. (3a) – casting mold filled with NaAlg. (3b) – extraction of the inner cylinder of the mold. (3c) – extraction of the alginate scaffold from the mold. (3d) – extracted scaffold.

A set of cylinders was used as the casting mold. A fluoroplastic tube with dimensions 3*4 mm and the same length (100 mm) was placed over a metal rod with a diameter of 3 mm and a length of 100 mm. Over this fluoroplastic tube, a second fluoroplastic tube with dimensions 4*5.2 mm and half the length was externally placed. Subsequently, an additional fluoroplastic tube with dimensions 6*8 mm and full length was placed over the outer tube, and a final metal cylinder with dimensions 8*10 mm was placed over it.

The remaining upper volume of the gap was filled under sterile conditions with 1 ml of alginate solution obtained during the evaporation concentration stage. The filled mold was placed in sealed conical tubes and incubated for 4 cycles: 10 minutes at a temperature of +41°C, followed by 20 minutes at a temperature of -18°C.

Upon completion of the final freezing stage, the mold was brought to room temperature (+21°C) for 1 minute to soften the scaffold walls. Subsequently, the inner rod was extracted in the direction of the filled mold directly into a cooled (+4°C) 1.1% (w/v) CaCl₂ solution. In this process, the fluoroplastic intermediate rod acted as an injector for the alginate matrix, while the walls of the outer cylinder served to maintain the geometric shape until the scaffold entered the cross-linking solution. After entry, the calcium chloride solution itself assumed the function of maintaining and simultaneously reinforcing the scaffold's shape, acting as an ionic cross-linking agent.

After removal from the casting mold, the inner rod with the attached matrix was placed back into a sealed conical tube containing 1.1% (w/v) CaCl₂ solution and incubated at 4 °C for 1 hour to continue chemical cross-linking.

Upon completion of the preliminary incubation, the inner rod and matrix were extracted from the conical tube. Then, the fluoroplastic tube was also extracted in the direction of the matrix, again serving as an injector for the matrix form. This ensured a controlled, unobstructed disassembly of the matrix form while minimizing perpendicular exogenous (external) pressure required for its extraction from the rod surface.

After the final removal from the mold, the alginate matrix was once again placed in a sealed conical tube with 1.1% (w/v) CaCl₂ solution and incubated at 4 °C for 1 hour to complete sufficient cross-linking.

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